

JOURNAL OF BIOCHEMISTRY PHARMACOLOGY AND PUBLIC HEALTH

Volume: 3 Issue: 1

January-March, 2025

ISSN-2958-762X

DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Research Article

KMF Publishers
www.kmf-publishers.com/jbpph/

OPEN ACCESS

Efficacy Of The Carestart Malaria Hrp2 And Pldh/Hrp2 Combo Compared To Microscopy In Diagnosis Of Malaria

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ABSTRACT

Malaria control involves prompt diagnosis of malaria parasites, either using microscopy, Rapid Diagnosis Test (RDTs), or other tools such as polymerase chain reaction (PCR). This study was conducted to observe the efficiency and effectiveness of microscopy and rapid diagnosis tests in detecting the malaria parasite. The study was conducted among patients visiting the Sir Yahaya Memorial Hospital Kebbi parasitology laboratory. Blood samples were collected and screened using microscopy and RDT according to the manufacturer's guidelines. The result of the study revealed high prevalence in patients within the age of 5-20 years with 41(68.33%) for microscopy and 40(66.67%) for RDT, out of 120 samples of patients, 75(62.50%) were male and 45(37.50%) were female, with positive 55(73.33%) for microscopy and positive of 49(65.33%) for RDT. Also, sensitivity, specificity, positive predicted value and negative predicted value of microscopy revealed a value of 100% while RDTs revealed 92.77%, 95.56%, 97.47% and 87.76%, respectively. This study revealed that microscopy remains the gold standard method for diagnosis of malaria, especially when there is available expertise, but in the absence of a microscope or its expertise, RDTs can be used for quick diagnosis of malaria parasite.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 10 January 2025

Revised 11 February 2025

Accepted 15 February 2025

KEYWORDS

Malaria, RDT, Sensitivity, Specificity, Patient

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INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a life-threatening illness that has continued to pose public health challenges. It affects millions of people all around the globe, especially in Africa, Asia and South America. Malaria is currently endemic in over 100 countries, with 3 billion people at risk of infection and around 225 million cases in 2009, leading to approximately 781,000 deaths (WHO, 2010). Malaria has remained a significant public health problem in Nigeria and is responsible for 30% of childhood and 11% of maternal mortality (FMOH, 2005). It accounts for 300,000 deaths each year and about 60% of outpatient visits (President's Malaria Initiative, 2011). Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of Congo account for over 40% of the estimated malaria burden and deaths globally (WHO, 2012). It is caused by the asexual form of the parasitic protozoan known as Plasmodium. The species incriminated are Plasmodium falciparum, Plasmodium vivax, Plasmodium malariae, and Plasmodium ovale, which are found in humans, and Plasmodium knowlesi, which is found in non-humans. Among these parasites, Plasmodium falciparum and Plasmodium vivax are the most widespread and common causes of mixed-species malaria, which is defined as co-infection with more than one species or genotype of Plasmodium (Mayxay et al., 2004). Most cases of malaria are uncomplicated, commonly presenting with fever and sometimes with other non-specific symptoms, including headache, aches, and pains elsewhere in the body (Gilles, 1991; WHO, 2003). Note that early diagnosis and treatment

are key to addressing morbidity and mortality due to malaria. Proper management of malaria cases within the first 24 hours of onset is considered the best way to reduce morbidity and mortality (Singh et al., 2013). This would be adequately achieved if most patients could access laboratory facilities (Kamugisha et al., 2008). Most victims of malaria still die because the disease is not diagnosed in time by health workers (Uzochukwu et al., 2009). Microscopy is the gold standard for laboratory diagnosis of malaria in many developing countries, though expertise may be lacking in both endemic and non-endemic settings (Moody, 2002), especially in Nigeria. However, in situations lacking reliable microscopic diagnosis, rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) may offer a valuable alternative to microscopy (Nour et al., 2009).

RDTs are generally fast, easy to perform, and relatively cheap (Lubell et al., 2007). Much research and development has been done to develop alternative methods for laboratory malaria diagnosis. Rapid diagnostic tests have been developed, validated, and field-tested. It was introduced in the nineties but has undergone many improvements (Martha et al., 2010). Malaria rapid diagnostic tests play a key role in malaria control and elimination programs to avoid unnecessary anti-malarial therapy, prevent drug resistance, and enhance case finding (Eibach et al., 2013). More than 60 RDT brands and over 200 different products have been developed. The WHO and Foundation for Innovative New Diagnostics (FIND) evaluated

70 from 26 manufacturers (WHO, 2008; 2009). Of these products, 39 are three-band tests that detect and differentiate *P. falciparum* from non-falciparum species (Martha et al., 2010). The CareStar Malaria HRP-2/pLDH (Pf/pan) Combo Test and the SD Bioline Ag pf/pan, HRP-2,2 and pan-pLDH are three-band DTs detecting HRP-2 and pan-pLDH. This present study is focused on evaluating the efficacy of the many RDTs. Malaria kits use microscopy tests as the gold standard for diagnosing malaria. Ria.SD Bioline (Ag pf/pan, Cassette, RDT, kit) is a one-step differential diagnosis by detecting HRP-II antigen from *Plasmodium falciparum* and pLDH antigen from other species (*P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, *P. ovale*) in human whole blood. The CareStart (Combo, dev., RDT) is a test designed for the differential diagnosis between *Plasmodium falciparum* and other *Plasmodium* species, such as *Plasmodium vivax*, *Plasmodium ovale*, and *Plasmodium malariae*. Though the gold standard for malaria testing remains microscopy, the limitations associated with this technique could affect the speed of delivery of quality services to the patients (Ameh et al., 2012).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials and Equipment

S/N	Equipment	Model
1	Autoclave	ST19T
2	Microscope	AC220V 50H2
3	Syringe	
List of Apparatus/Glassware		
4	Oil immersion	
5	Physiological saline	
6	Cotton wool	
7	Glass slide	

Study Area

The study was carried out at Sir Yahya Memorial Hospital (SYMh). Sir Yahaya is located in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria and was built in 1952 with native authority funds. It was commissioned in December 1952 as a general hospital with a maternity ward and three wards, one male and two female wards and also located at the latitude of 12.455511oN and a longitude of 4.200038oE. The hospital is over 290 capacity 290-bed facility headed by a Chief Medical Director (CMD). Management and funding of the general hospital underwent dynamic changes from Gwandu native authority to northern Nigerian government to northwestern state government to sokoto government and now kebbi as from August 1991. On the creation of Kebbi, the hospital was upgraded to a specialist hospital and in 1997 also renamed as Sir Yahya Memorial Hospital Birnin Kebbi to immortalise the 17th Emir of Gwandu who had a vision to build a hospital at that time on his farmland without soliciting for compensation.

Birnin Kebbi is located on latitude 12.453611oN and longitude 4.200278oE. Birnin Kebbi is located in northwestern Nigeria—a capital city of Kebbi State and the headquarters of Gwandu Emirate. As of 2007, the population estimated is 125,594. It is also primarily a Hausa and Fulani state with Islam as the primary religion. Birnin Kebbi is located on the Sokoto River and is connected by road to Argungu (45km northeast), Jega (35km southeast), and Bunza(45km southwest). The Fulani ethnic group dominates the city. The climate of Birnin Kebbi is a local step climate. There is little rainfall throughout the year. The average temperature is 33 ° C, and April is the hottest month with an average of 104 ° F. (Sir yahya hospital.com)

Ethical Consideration

The Kebbi State Ministry of Health's ethical committee approved the study. Before administering the work, the health professionals signed an informed letter.

Study Population

The study population included all patients referred to the laboratory suspected of malaria: one hundred twenty (120) patients from Sir Yahya Hospital Kebbi.

Collection of Specimen

The method of sample collection employed was the venipuncture technique (Okocha et al., 2005; Epidi et al., 2008). A soft tubing tourniquet was fastened to the patient's upper arm to enable the index finger to feel a suitable vein. The puncture site was then cleansed with methylated spirit

(methanol), and venepuncture was made with the aid of a 23 G needle attached to a 2 mL syringe. When sufficient blood had been collected, the tourniquet was released and the needle removed immediately while the blood was transferred into an EDTA bottle (Epidi et al., 2008).

Sample Processing

Microscopy

The collected blood samples were analysed within 1 to 2 h of collection. Thick and thin blood films were prepared according to the technique outlined by Cheesebrough (2004) and described by Epidi et al. (2008). 6ul A blood sample of 6ul was placed in the center of a grease-free, clean glass slide for a thick smear and 2ul for a thin smear. Thereafter, the reverse side of the slide was cleaned with cotton wool and kept for air-drying and staining with field's stain. The thin film side was fixed gently with methanol for 30 seconds. The slide was flooded with 10% Giemsa stain solution for 15m. It was washed off gently in clean water. The back of the slide was cleaned with cotton wool and kept in the draining rack to air-dry for eventual examination under the microscope, using oil immersion at X100 magnification to observe for Plasmodium parasites—the presence of ring forms of Plasmodium and Trophozoites of Plasmodium indicate positive results. A blood smear was considered harmful if no parasite was seen after 10 min of search or examination under 100 high-power microscope fields.

Parasite density per microliter of blood (parasitemia) was estimated from the thick film,

taking the number of leucocytes per microliter of blood as 8,000 and was expressed as follows:

Parasite density/ μL = Parasite count x 8,000 (Hammamiet al., 2013)

No. of WBC counted

Test Procedure for (CareStart Malaria Test Kit)

The procedures for both RDTs were similar; the area to be lanced was cleaned with an alcohol swab. The end of the patient's fingertip was squeezed and pricked with a sterile lancet provided; the first drop of blood was wiped away with sterile cotton. A sample was taken with the pipette, and while gently squeezing the tube, I immersed the open end in the blood drop and gently released the pressure to draw blood into the sample pipette up to the black line. Add 5 μl

of whole blood was drop into the Sample Well (small well). I also added two drops (60 μl) of assay buffer into the buffer well. Finally, the test result was read in 20 minutes. (Tjitraet al., 1999)

Determination of Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV and NPV of RDTs

The sensitivity of RDT was determined by taking the percentage of positive malaria tests by RDT from the total number of malaria-positive samples by microscopy. It was calculated using the formula below;

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative}} \times 100$$

Sensitivity is a measure of how well a test can identify true positives (medcalc.org)

Percentage of malaria Negative test by RDT from the total number of malaria negative samples by microscopy. It was calculated using the formula below;

Specificity: -Was determined by taking the

$$\text{specificity} = \frac{\text{True Negative}}{\text{True Negative} + \text{False Positive}} \times 100$$

Specificity is a measure of how well a test can identify a true negative (medcalc.org)

Those who tested positive by a rapid diagnostic test were genuinely infected. Below is the formula used to calculate PPV (Thomas, 2011).

Positive Predictive Value

Is the probability that those individual testing

$$\text{Positive Predictive Value} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative}} \times 100$$

Negative Predictive Value
Is the probability that those individuals who test negative by rapid diagnostic test were truly

uninfected? Below is the formula (Thomas, 2011).

$$\text{Negative Predicted Value} = \frac{\text{True Negative}}{\text{True Negative} + \text{False Negative}} \times 100$$

and negative predictive values were calculated by comparing them with a standard 100% confidence level.

DATA ANALYSIS

The chi-square was used as a statistical tool to test the study's hypothesis. The null hypothesis was tested with a chi-square at a 0.05 significance level. The sensitivity, specificity, and positive

RESULTS

Table 4.1: Age Distribution of Malaria Parasite by Microscopy and RDTs

Age	Microscopy		RDT	
	Positive Sample	Negative Sample	Positive Sample	Negative Sample
0-5yrs	14(70.00%)	6(30.00%)	12(60.00%)	8(40.00%)
5-20yrs	41(68.33%)	19(31.67%)	40(66.67%)	20(33.33%)
20-above	27(67.50%)	13(32.50%)	25(62.50%)	15(37.50%)

Keys: Rapid diagnosis test (RDT), Years (yrs.), Percentage (%)

The study participants were categorised as 0- 5 yrs, 5- 20 yrs, and 20- above. The microscopy result showed that 14, 41, and 27 were positive for the age, respectively. The result of the study reveals that people within the age of 5-20yrs have the highest malaria incidence with 41 positive cases, while 0-5yrs have lowest case of malaria

with 14 cases. The RDTs test results show that the malaria parasite case is higher among ages 5-20yrs with 40 positive cases and also lowest in those under 0-5yrs with 12 positive cases out of 77 positive cases described in table 4.1.

Table 4.2: Sex Distribution of Malaria parasites by Microscopy and RDTs

Sex	No of Sample	Microscopy		RDTs	
		Positive Sample	Negative Sample	Positive Sample	Negative Sample
Male	75(62.50%)	55(73.33%)	20(26.67%)	49(65.33%)	26(34.67%)
Female	45(37.50%)	30(66.67%)	15(33.33%)	27(60.00%)	18(40.00%)

Keys: Number (No), Rapid diagnosis test (RDT), Percentage (%)

The results of the distribution of malaria parasites by microscopy and RDT were used to determine the sex of the study participants. The study results show that the number of malaria-positive cases is high among males, with 75 positive cases, and less among females, with 45 malaria-positive cases. Also, the sex distribution of malaria parasites by rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) showed that out of 120 study participants

tested, 76 were positive for malaria parasites, and both males and females were found to be 49 and 27, respectively. This indicates that male participants were highly infected with the malaria parasite than females. 55(73.33%) positive cases detected by microscopy are males, while 30(66.67%) are female. Also RDT cases with 49(65.33%) are male and 27(60.00%) are female.

Table 4.3: Comparison of Microscopy with RDT

	Positive	Negative	True Positive	False Positive	True Negative	False Negative
Microscopy	82	38	82	0	38	0
RDT	77	43	75	2	37	6

Keys: Rapid diagnosis test (RDT)

This shows the comparison of microscopy results with RDT results. For microscopy, 82 samples tested positive, while 38 were negative for malaria parasites. For RDTs, 77 samples tested positive, and 43 samples were negative. Among

the 82 positive cases diagnosed by microscopy, RDT failed to detect 6 cases that tested positive by microscopy, yielding a false negative result. Also, among the 38 negative cases detected by microscopy, 2 were RDT positive, yielding two

false positive results. So, a high positive value of 82 was obtained by microscopy, while RDT has a positive value of 77.

Table 4.4: Sensitivity, specificity, Positive Predictive Value (PPV) and Negative Predictive Value (NPV) of Microscopy and RDT

	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)
Microscopy	100	100	100	100
RDT	92.77	95.56	97.47	87.76

Keys: positive predicted value (PPV), Negative predicted value (NPV), Rapid diagnosis test (RDT), and Percentage (%)

The performance of both RDT and microscopy presented below shows that microscopy has a sensitivity, specificity, positive predicted value, and negative predicted value of 100%. Meanwhile, RDT shows a sensitivity of 92.77, a

specificity of 95.56, a positive predicted value of 97.47, and a negative predicted value of 87.76. Microscopy has higher sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV than RDT.

Table 4.5: Mixed Species of Malaria Infection Detected By Microscopy and RDT

	No. of Positive Samples	Single Species	Mixed Species
Microscopy	82	62	20
RDT	77	58	19
Total	159	120	39

Keys: Number (No), Rapid diagnosis test (RDT)

Both microscopy and RDT detected mixed species of malaria parasites. Microscopy shows that 20 out of 82 positive samples indicated mixed species of malaria parasites, while RDT shows that 19 out of 77 positive samples

indicated mixed species of malaria parasites. RDT detects plasmodium that only infect humans, depending on the antigens on which they are based. Some detect falciparum only, while some combine with other plasmodia

indicated on two separate bands.

DISCUSSION

Based on the experimental study, 120 patients were recruited for the study. Blood samples were collected from patients visiting Sir Yahya Memorial Hospital. The results of the test were recorded immediately after each test. Microscopic analysis showed 62.50% (75/120) of the sample were male and 37.50% (45/120) female. Of the blood slides, 73.33% (55/75) were positive for malaria parasitemia in males and 66.67% (30/45) in females. Hence, microscopy was used as the control for the study. The malaria rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) used were CareStart AgPf/Pan. It is expected that typical malaria RDTs should have a high sensitivity of 95%, a specificity of 97%, and the ability to detect low parasite density infections (WHO, 2003). The finding of this study is slightly contrary as the results from CareStart indicate otherwise, compared to the World Health Organization's standardisation for RDTs.

In Table 4.2, RDT showed 65.33% (49/75) positive by male and 60.00% (27/45) in female. The sensitivity was 92.77%, and the specificity was 95.56%, with a positive predicted value of 97.47 and a negative predicted value of 87.76, while microscopy showed 100%, respectively. The findings in this study are in agreement with the studies by Mohammed and Bilyaminu in (2019), which shows that sensitivity and specificity of CareStart falls within the ranges of (93.29-100%) and (93.81-100%) respectively (Mahende et al., 2016; Garba et al., 2006). In

addition, malaria incidence was higher in males than in females by both microscopy and RDT, as indicated in Table 4.2. The reason here may be that men spend more time outside than women, engaging in some activities in one way or another, which may be around the breeding sites of the parasite. However, only a single microscope that competes for several other microscopic examinations can be a limitation. While the gold standard for malaria testing remains microscopy, the limitations associated with this technique could affect the speed of delivery of quality services to the patients.

CONCLUSION

This study showed that the efficacy and performance of CareStart Ag-Pf/pan RDTs are rapid and straightforward to perform, and the results can be interpreted by anyone or healthcare workers. CareStart Ag-Pf/pan is a valuable test that has shown desirable results in alleviating the diagnostic challenges faced by many people who cannot access microscopic services for malaria diagnosis in Nigeria. This study's results also indicate that RDTs should be evaluated in each new setting before being deployed, given possible variations in performance in different populations. Conclusively, while the gold standard for malaria testing remains microscopy, the limitations associated with this technique could affect the speed of delivery of quality services to the patients, especially in endemic areas. RDTs will directly help to target malaria treatment in areas where microscopy is poor; ongoing evaluations of field use accuracy and further studies on potential factors affecting the

sensitivity and specificity of RDTs are proposed. Hence, the RDT can become a good screening test for the diagnosis of malaria in the laboratory.

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